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Job satisfaction of selected Filipino teachers working in Philippine public schools and in U.S. public schools: A comparative study

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Abstract

There is a steady migration of Filipino teachers to the US, while teachers that remain in the Philippines face a number of challenges. This study sought to ascertain whether a difference exists between the job satisfaction levels of Filipino teachers based in the Philippines and those based in the US. Through snowball and quota sampling, 30 Filipino teachers working in Philippine public schools and 30 Filipino teachers working in US public schools were invited to participate in this research. The Teacher Job Satisfaction Scale 9-item questionnaire (TJSS-9) was used as the instrument for this study. The results revealed that for the domain of satisfaction with co-workers, Filipino teachers based in the US had higher levels of job satisfaction. But for the domains of student discipline and parental involvement, the Filipino teachers based in the Philippines had higher levels of job satisfaction. However, t-test results indicate that these differences were not statistically significant.

Keywords: Filipino Teacher; Teacher Job Satisfaction Scale; Overseas Filipino Worker; Philippines

1. Introduction

The Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines mandates that the priority of the national budget goes to education.¹ The country has nearly 900,000 public school teachers in all levels of basic education. In 2020, there is an estimated 28 million students enrolled.² Despite this, many Filipino children drop out of school early, which makes basic education a challenging issue in the Philippines.¹

Across the nation, over 60,000 institutions offer instruction at various levels of basic education, indicating a slight reduction in number from the almost 62,000 schools prior to the COVID-19 pandemic. In the case of Department of Education, it is reported that 98 percent of all public schools in the country possess electricity and 95.8 percent of them have access to water, while over 80 percent have computers.²

However, certain working conditions in the Philippines are causing an increasing number of teachers to find employment abroad. 92 percent of public school teachers are paid a salary between P25,000 to P30,000 a month, which constitutes a significant factor in this job migration. Since 75 percent of basic education teachers are hired by the government, there is a clamor for certain changes.³

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Public school teachers often face unreasonable burdens such as being assigned to teach 90 students in one class. Facilities remain inadequate as well as a shortage of classrooms. The pandemic forced teachers to conduct online instruction with insufficient computer resources and connectivity. On top of all this, additional administrative tasks are given to teachers.²

According to one survey, 52.9% of Philippine youth aged 15-35 would like to work overseas.⁴ Due to Filipinos' proficiency in the English language many consider employment abroad, including teachers. There are an estimated 2.2 million Overseas Filipino Workers. And according to job migration trends recorded by the Philippine Overseas Employment Administration (POEA), the Philippines deploys an average of 1,500 teachers abroad annually.⁵

One such country that requires teachers is the United States. In 2018, the US had an estimated teacher shortage of 112,000. Many Filipino teachers try to fill this need by applying for a J-1 visa, which allows them to stay in the US for up to 5 years. In a state like Arizona, the average starting pay is 36,300 USD. In the Philippines, there are several placement agencies which can process employment in the US within a 2-month period.⁶

Filipinos teaching overseas are known for their competence in teaching the English language, which is why there is a demand for them.⁵ They are also known to be hardworking and patient. But many of them experience culture shock. One challenge faced by Filipino teachers in the US is classroom management. US students have been observed to behave differently than Filipino students in terms of discipline.⁶

There appear to be challenges for the Filipino teacher no matter where he or she teaches. And job performance has been shown to be influenced by the degree of job satisfaction experienced.⁷

In one study, it was found that teachers' job satisfaction was negatively related to job stress, that cultural context influences motivation beliefs and it also establishes the importance of collective motivation as a source of individual job satisfaction.⁸

In another study, workload and student behavior were found to be significant predictors in the occurrence of depression in teachers. Years of teaching experience was also established to be a significant and positive predictor of job satisfaction.⁹

One study found that the school administrator's leadership behavior was significantly related to the job satisfaction of teachers.¹⁰ Age and working experience also greatly contributed to the teacher's job satisfaction.¹¹

In terms of other predictors of teacher job satisfaction, effective professional development, teacher cooperation, student-teacher relationship, teacher self-efficacy, participation of stakeholders, school autonomy for instruction, principal job satisfaction, school location, classroom discipline climate were found to be among them by another study.¹² However, one study claims that teacher-level variables are better predictors of job satisfaction than school variables.¹³

In yet another study, job status, financial and physical resources of the school and supervision were related to teachers' job satisfaction. But salary as a factor was not found to be an important factor.¹⁴ Schools must take care of interpersonal relations especially at the classroom level, according to one study.¹³ It was also found that each teacher's relationship with every other teacher predicted the development of teacher job satisfaction.¹⁶

As for Filipino teachers based in the Philippines, one study suggests that efforts be made to improve workload and employment conditions⁹. Concerning the students who are the clients of teachers, in order to enhance their academic performance one study recommends an atmosphere that promotes the interpersonal relationships of the teacher.¹⁴

Based on the observed migration of Filipino teachers abroad, and the prevailing conditions that Filipino teachers face in the Philippines, this study sought to compare the job satisfaction of teachers working in government schools in the US and in the Philippines. To assess this, the Teacher Job Satisfaction Scale 9-item questionnaire (TJSS-9) was used.¹⁵

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the levels of job satisfaction of Filipino teachers working in Philippine public schools as measured by the TJSS-9 in terms of
 - a) Satisfaction with Coworkers;

- b) Satisfaction with Student Discipline;
 - c) Satisfaction with Parental Involvement?
2. What are the levels of job satisfaction of Filipino teachers working in US public schools as measured by the TJSS-9 in terms of
- a) Satisfaction with Coworkers;
 - b) Satisfaction with Student Discipline;
 - c) Satisfaction with Parental Involvement?
3. Is there a significant difference in the levels of job satisfaction of Filipino teachers working in Philippine public schools and those working in US public schools as measured by the TJSS-9 in terms of
- a) Satisfaction with Coworkers;
 - b) Satisfaction with Student Discipline;
 - c) Satisfaction with Parental Involvement;
 - d) overall?
4. Is there a significant difference in the job satisfaction when grouped according to sex among
- a) Filipino teachers in the Philippines;
 - b) Filipino teachers in the US?
5. Is there a significant difference in the job satisfaction of teachers when grouped according to civil status among
- a) Filipino teachers in the Philippines;
 - b) Filipino teachers in the US?

2. Methodology

Through quota and snowball sampling, 30 Filipino teachers in public schools in the Philippines and 30 Filipino teachers in public schools in the US were invited to participate in this study.

Among the Filipino teachers based in the Philippines, 4 had bachelor's degrees, 12 had master's units, 3 had a master's degree, 8 had doctoral units and 3 had doctorate degrees. 11 were males and 19 were females. 14 were single while 16 were married.

Among the Filipino teachers based in the US, 1 of them had only a bachelor's degrees, 14 had master's units, 10 had a master's degree, 2 had doctoral units and 3 had doctorate degrees. 11 were males and 19 were females. 12 were single while 18 were married.

The Teacher Job Satisfaction Scale 9-item questionnaire (TJSS-9) was employed in this research. It measures 3 domains, namely, (1) Satisfaction with Coworkers, (2) Satisfaction with Student Discipline and (3) Satisfaction with Parental Involvement. This instrument has displayed robust psychometric properties in a study conducted in 6 different countries.¹⁵ The instrument was administered online through Google Forms. The participants' identities were kept anonymous and their informed consent was obtained.

3. Results

The following are tables that show the data gathered and the statistical treatments utilized.

Table 1 Educational Background of the Respondents

	Bachelor's degree	Bachelor's degree with master's units	Master's degree	Master's degree with doctoral units	Doctorate
Philippines	4	12	3	8	3
US	1	14	10	2	3

Table 2 Sex of the Respondents

	Male	Female
Philippines	11	19
US	11	19

Table 3 Civil Status of the Respondents

	Single	Married
Philippines	14	16
US	12	18

Table 4 Teachers' Job Satisfaction Survey Scale of Interpretation

Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.00 - 1.80	Highly dissatisfied
1.81 - 2.60	Dissatisfied
2.61 - 3.40	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
3.41 - 4.20	Satisfied
4.21 - 5.00	Highly satisfied

Table 5 TJSS Responses per Item of Filipino Teachers in the Philippines

Item	Weighted Mean N=30	Verbal Interpretation
Satisfaction with Coworkers		
The quality of your relations with co-workers	3.9	Satisfied
The extent to which your co-workers encourage you and support you in your work	4.033333333	Satisfied
Your overall satisfaction with your co-workers	3.933333333	Satisfied
Satisfaction with Student Discipline		
The extent to which students act in a self-disciplined manner	3.633333333	Satisfied
Your satisfaction with the behavior of students in your school	3.3	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied

Your overall level of satisfaction with student discipline in your school	3.533333333	Satisfied
Satisfaction with Parental Involvement		
The degree of interest shown by parents in the education of their children	3.5	Satisfied
The extent to which parents are supportive of the school and its programs	3.533333333	Satisfied
Your overall level of satisfaction with parents where you work	3.533333333	Satisfied

Table 6 TJSS Responses per Item of Filipino Teachers in the US

Item	Weighted Mean N=30	Verbal Interpretation
Satisfaction with Coworkers		
The quality of your relations with co-workers	4.2	Satisfied
The extent to which your co-workers encourage you and support you in your work	4.233333333	Highly satisfied
Your overall satisfaction with your co-workers	4.233333333	Highly satisfied
Satisfaction with Student Discipline		
The extent to which students act in a self-disciplined manner	3.233333333	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
Your satisfaction with the behavior of students in your school	3.1	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
Your overall level of satisfaction with student discipline in your school	3.2	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
Satisfaction with Parental Involvement		
The degree of interest shown by parents in the education of their children	3.366666667	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
The extent to which parents are supportive of the school and its programs	3.366666667	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
Your overall level of satisfaction with parents where you work	3.333333333	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied

Table 7 Comparison of TJSS Responses per Item between Filipino Teachers in the Philippines and in the US

Item	Teachers in the Philippines	Comparison	Teachers in the US
Satisfaction with Coworkers			
The quality of your relations with co-workers	3.9	<	4.2
The extent to which your co-workers encourage you and support you in your work	4.033333333	<	4.233333333
Your overall satisfaction with your co-workers	3.933333333	<	4.233333333

Satisfaction with Student Discipline			
The extent to which students act in a self-disciplined manner	3.633333333	>	3.233333333
Your satisfaction with the behavior of students in your school	3.3	>	3.1
Your overall level of satisfaction with student discipline in your school	3.533333333	>	3.2
Satisfaction with Parental Involvement			
The degree of interest shown by parents in the education of their children	3.5	>	3.366666667
The extent to which parents are supportive of the school and its programs	3.533333333	>	3.366666667
Your overall level of satisfaction with parents where you work	3.533333333	>	3.333333333

Table 8 Difference in the *Satisfaction with Coworkers* between Filipino Teachers in the Philippines and in the US

T-test Results	
<p>Philippines N1: 30 $df1 = N - 1 = 30 - 1 = 29$ M1: 3.96 SS1: 20.61 $s21 = SS1/(N - 1) = 20.61/(30-1) = 0.71$</p>	<p>US N2: 30 $df2 = N - 1 = 30 - 1 = 29$ M2: 4.22 SS2: 16.96 $s22 = SS2/(N - 1) = 16.96/(30-1) = 0.58$</p>
<p>T-value Calculation $s2p = ((df1/(df1 + df2)) * s21) + ((df2/(df2 + df2)) * s22) = ((29/58) * 0.71) + ((29/58) * 0.58) = 0.65$ $s2M1 = s2p/N1 = 0.65/30 = 0.02$ $s2M2 = s2p/N2 = 0.65/30 = 0.02$ $t = (M1 - M2)/\sqrt{(s2M1 + s2M2)} = -0.27/\sqrt{0.04} = -1.28$ The t-value is -1.28323. The p-value is .204514. The result is not significant at $p < .05$.</p>	

Table 9 Difference in the *Satisfaction with Student Discipline* between Filipino Teachers in the Philippines and in the US

T-test Results	
<p>Philippine N1: 30 $df1 = N - 1 = 30 - 1 = 29$ M1: 3.76 SS1: 18.36 $s21 = SS1/(N - 1) = 18.36/(30-1) = 0.63$</p>	<p>US N2: 30 $df2 = N - 1 = 30 - 1 = 29$ M2: 3.77 SS2: 10.62 $s22 = SS2/(N - 1) = 10.62/(30-1) = 0.37$</p>
<p>T-value Calculation $s2p = ((df1/(df1 + df2)) * s21) + ((df2/(df2 + df2)) * s22) = ((29/58) * 0.63) + ((29/58) * 0.37) = 0.5$ $s2M1 = s2p/N1 = 0.5/30 = 0.02$</p>	

$s^2M2 = s^2p/N2 = 0.5/30 = 0.02$ $t = (M1 - M2)/\sqrt{(s^2M1 + s^2M2)} = -0.02/\sqrt{0.03} = -0.1$ The t-value is -0.10437. The p-value is .917238. The result is not significant at $p < .05$.

Table 10 Difference in the *Satisfaction with Parental Involvement* between Filipino Teachers in the Philippines and in the US

T-test Results	
Philippines N1: 30 $df1 = N - 1 = 30 - 1 = 29$ M1: 3.69 SS1: 16.76 $s^2_1 = SS1/(N - 1) = 16.76/(30-1) = 0.58$	US N2: 30 $df2 = N - 1 = 30 - 1 = 29$ M2: 3.66 SS2: 11.03 $s^2_2 = SS2/(N - 1) = 11.03/(30-1) = 0.38$
T-value Calculation $s^2p = ((df1/(df1 + df2)) * s^2_1) + ((df2/(df2 + df2)) * s^2_2) = ((29/58) * 0.58) + ((29/58) * 0.38) = 0.48$ $s^2M1 = s^2p/N1 = 0.48/30 = 0.02$ $s^2M2 = s^2p/N2 = 0.48/30 = 0.02$ $t = (M1 - M2)/\sqrt{(s^2M1 + s^2M2)} = 0.03/\sqrt{0.03} = 0.18$ The t-value is 0.17682. The p-value is .860263. The result is not significant at $p < .05$.	

Table 11 Difference in the Overall TJSS Scores between Filipino Teachers in the Philippines and in the US

T-test Results	
Philippines N1: 30 $df1 = N - 1 = 30 - 1 = 29$ M1: 3.66 SS1: 16.75 $s^2_1 = SS1/(N - 1) = 16.75/(30-1) = 0.58$	US N2: 30 $df2 = N - 1 = 30 - 1 = 29$ M2: 3.59 SS2: 11.78 $s^2_2 = SS2/(N - 1) = 11.78/(30-1) = 0.41$
T-value Calculation $s^2p = ((df1/(df1 + df2)) * s^2_1) + ((df2/(df2 + df2)) * s^2_2) = ((29/58) * 0.58) + ((29/58) * 0.41) = 0.49$ $s^2M1 = s^2p/N1 = 0.49/30 = 0.02$ $s^2M2 = s^2p/N2 = 0.49/30 = 0.02$ $t = (M1 - M2)/\sqrt{(s^2M1 + s^2M2)} = 0.07/\sqrt{0.03} = 0.39$ The t-value is 0.38863. The p-value is .698975. The result is not significant at $p < .05$.	

Table 12 Difference in TJSS Scores between Male and Female Filipino Teachers in the Philippines

Welch t test results		
Group	Male	Female
Mean	3.35353535345	3.83040935679
SD	0.77271076760	0.71469814913
SEM	0.23298106251	0.16396300038
N	11	19
Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 1.6739 df = 19 standard error of difference = 0.285		
P value and statistical significance: P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.1105 Not statistically significant. Confidence interval: The mean of Male minus Female equals -0.47687400333 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -1.07316218678 to 0.11941418011		

Table 13 Difference in TJSS Scores between Male and Female Filipino Teachers in the US

Welch t test results		
Group	Male	Female
Mean	3.72727272727	3.50292397642
SD	0.84526807257	0.48766460225
SEM	0.25485791309	0.11187793261
N	11	19
Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 0.8060 df = 13 standard error of difference = 0.278		
P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.4347 Not statistically significant. Confidence interval: The mean of Male minus Female equals 0.22434875085 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -0.37695305818 to 0.82565055988		

Table 14 Difference in TJSS Scores between Single and Married Filipino Teachers in the Philippines

Welch t test results		
Group	Single	Married
Mean	3.79365079371	3.53472222219
SD	0.63284152872	0.85799915576
SEM	0.16913401290	0.21449978894
N	14	16
Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 0.9479 df = 27 standard error of difference = 0.273		
P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.3516 Not statistically significant. Confidence interval: The mean of Single minus Married equals 0.25892857153 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -0.30154996096 to 0.81940710401		

Table 15 Difference in TJSS Scores between Single and Married Filipino Teachers in the US

Welch t test results		
Group	Single	Married
Mean	3.39814814808	3.70987654306
SD	0.81161369987	0.47468812367
SEM	0.23429269405	0.11188506373
N	12	18
Intermediate values used in calculations: t = 1.2006 df = 16 standard error of difference = 0.260		
P value and statistical significance: The two-tailed P value equals 0.2474 Not statistically significant. Confidence interval: The mean of Single minus Married equals -0.31172839497 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -0.86213379790 to 0.23867700795		

4. Discussion

Table 5 shows the TJSS-9 responses of Filipino teachers based in the Philippines. The respondents were satisfied with the quality of their relations with co-workers, the extent to which their co-workers encourage them and support them in their work and in their overall satisfaction with their co-workers.

The Filipino teachers based in the Philippines were also satisfied with the extent to which students act in a self-disciplined manner, but were neither satisfied or dissatisfied with the behavior of students in their school, and were satisfied with the overall level of satisfaction with student discipline in their school

The Filipino teachers based in the Philippines were also satisfied with the degree of interest shown by parents in the education of their children, in the extent to which parents are supportive of the school and its programs and in their overall level of satisfaction with parents where they work.

Table 6 shows the TJSS-9 responses of Filipino teachers based in the US. The respondents were satisfied with the quality of their relations with co-workers, highly satisfied with the extent to which their co-workers encourage them and support them in their work and highly satisfied in their overall satisfaction with their co-workers.

The Filipino teachers based in the US were neither satisfied or dissatisfied with the extent to which students act in a self-disciplined manner, but were neither satisfied or dissatisfied with the behavior of students in their school, and were neither satisfied or dissatisfied with the overall level of satisfaction with student discipline in their school

The Filipino teachers based in the US were neither satisfied or dissatisfied with the degree of interest shown by parents in the education of their children, neither satisfied or dissatisfied in the extent to which parents are supportive of the school and its programs and neither satisfied or dissatisfied in their overall level of satisfaction with parents where they work.

Table 7 shows the comparison of TJSS-9 responses of Filipino teachers based in the Philippines and in the US. Filipino teachers based in the US had a higher level of satisfaction with the quality of their relations with co-workers, with the extent to which their co-workers encourage them and support them in their work and in their overall satisfaction with their co-workers, as compared to Filipino teachers based in the Philippines.

However, Filipino teachers based in the Philippines had a higher level of satisfaction with the extent to which students act in a self-disciplined manner, with the behavior of students in their school, and with the overall level of satisfaction with student discipline in their school as compared to Filipino teachers based in the US.

Filipino teachers based in the Philippines also had a higher level of satisfaction with the degree of interest shown by parents in the education of their children, in the extent to which parents are supportive of the school and its programs and in their overall level of satisfaction with parents where they work as compared to Filipino teachers based in the US.

With respect to Satisfaction with Coworkers, Table 8 shows the independent t-test computation of the responses of Filipino teachers based in the Philippines and in the US. The t-value of -1.28 indicates that there is no significant difference between the 2 groups of respondents in this domain.

With respect to Satisfaction with Student Discipline, Table 9 shows the independent t-test computation of the responses of Filipino teachers based in the Philippines and in the US. The t-value of -0.1 indicates that there is no significant difference between the 2 groups of respondents in this domain.

With respect to Satisfaction with Students' Parental Involvement, Table 10 shows the independent t-test computation of the responses of Filipino teachers based in the Philippines and in the US. The t-value of 0.18 indicates that there is no significant difference between the 2 groups of respondents in this domain.

In terms of overall TJSS-9 scores in all 3 domains, Table 11 shows the independent t-test computation of the responses of Filipino teachers based in the Philippines and in the US. The t-value of 0.39 indicates that there is no significant difference between the 2 groups of respondents.

Table 12 shows the Welch's t-test computation between males and females among Filipino Teachers based in the Philippines. The two-tailed P value of 0.1105 indicates that there is no significant difference between males and females.

Table 13 shows the Welch's t-test computation between males and females among Filipino Teachers based in the US. The two-tailed P value of 0.4347 indicates that there is no significant difference between males and females.

Table 14 shows the Welch's t-test computation between single and married among Filipino Teachers based in the Philippines. The two-tailed P value of 0.3516 indicates that there is no significant difference between single and married respondents.

Table 15 shows the Welch's t-test computation between single and married among Filipino Teachers based in the US. The two-tailed P value of 0.2474 indicates that there is no significant difference between single and married respondents.

5. Conclusions

When looking at Table 7, at first there appears to be some difference in the responses of the two groups of Filipino teachers working in these two different countries. The Filipino teachers based in the US had higher levels of satisfaction with respect to co-workers, but these levels were lower in terms of student discipline and parental involvement.

In addition to the higher pay, perhaps another factor that sustains the perseverance of Filipino teachers based in the US is their high satisfaction with their co-workers as seen in Table 6.

Since overall, there was no significant difference found in the job satisfaction levels between both groups of respondents as measured by the TJSS-9, it would appear that as for the respondents of this study, the only clear advantage of being a Filipino teacher in the US is the higher pay.

Although this study is limited by the size of the sample, the sampling technique employed and the job satisfaction domains measured by the instrument utilized, the findings are of interest and merit further investigation.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All four authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in making this study.

Statement of informed consent

The informed consent of all the research participants was obtained, their identities were kept anonymous and the data acquired was used purely for the purpose of making this study.

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